

- 3D Printing Additive Manufacturing
- Stainless Steel Honeycomb Monolith

- Electrochemical Deposition
- Ce and Ni Incorporation

Highlights

- 3D printed metal honeycombs with different cells geometry and density active in DRM
- Easy and fast Ni and Ce electrodeposition leveraging support metallic nature
- Order of deposition strongly affects the performance in DRM reaction
- High conversion (>90%), selectivity ($H_2/CO=0.8$) and stability (>44 h) at 750 °C
- Great potential as alternative to structured catalysts prepared by washcoating

1 **Novel combination of 3D-printing and electrochemical**
2 **deposition to design and prepare metallic honeycomb**
3 **supported catalysts for dry reforming of methane**

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15

16 **ABSTRACT**

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18 A multidisciplinary approach has been followed for the development of
19 structured catalysts based on 3D-printed metallic honeycomb monoliths, which allows
20 overcoming some of the barriers that limit the industrial application of significant
21 catalytic processes such as those related to CO₂ valorization. In particular, nickel and/or
22 cerium-containing catalysts have been incorporated into stainless steel honeycombs and
23 evaluated in the Dry Reforming of Methane (DRM) reaction. Moreover, taking
24 advantage of the conductive nature of the metallic substrate, a methodology that allows
25 the incorporation of the active phase by electrochemical deposition has been
26 implemented. The prepared catalysts were characterized by SEM coupled EDX
27 compositional analysis, X-ray fluorescence, X-ray diffraction, X-ray Photoelectron
28 Spectroscopy and Temperature-Programmed Reduction. In contrast to the catalyst
29 where cerium and nickel were co-deposited, the catalyst obtained by sequential
30 electrodeposition of Ce (first) and Ni (second) proved to be highly active and stable in
31 the DRM process, with conversions of both CH₄ and CO₂ above 90% and H₂/CO ratio
32 of ca. 0.8 at 750 °C for more than 40 h. Moreover, the catalyst kept its good
33 performance after doubling the flow proving its great potential for a real application at
34 higher scale.

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38 *Keywords:* dry reforming of methane; electrodeposition; 3D printing, nickel/ceria
39 catalysts; stainless steel honeycomb.

40

41 **1. Introduction**

42

43 3D-printing technology, also known as additive manufacturing, has gained
44 widespread popularity and attention, and positioned at the forefront of modern materials
45 science and chemistry, including heterogeneous catalysis [1-4]. This is due to its eco-
46 friendly principle of layered manufacturing, in which a wide range of materials can be
47 engineered quickly through a simple layer-by-layer deposition route guided by a digital
48 design file [5-7].

49 3D-printing with metallic materials, often referred to as metal 3D-printing, is a
50 cutting-edge technology that permits the generation of three-dimensional objects made
51 of metal [8]. A wide range of metallic materials has been used, including stainless steel,
52 aluminum, titanium, Inconel, copper, or even precious metals such as gold, silver, or
53 platinum [7].

54 3D-printed metallic honeycomb monoliths represent a specialized application of
55 this technology, which combines the structural advantages of honeycomb geometries
56 with the material properties of metals [9,10].

57 Lately, the use of structured catalysts based on an active coating on metallic
58 monoliths (Al, stainless steel, FeCrAlloy, etc) represent significant alternatives to
59 pelletized catalysts for highly endothermic or exothermic processes [11,12]. However,
60 compared with ceramic substrates, they exhibit the drawback of a poorer adherence to
61 supported catalysts [13], a limitation that is routinely addressed by subsequent thermo-
62 chemical treatments that provide surface roughness to the metal onto which the
63 deposited phase may anchor [14]. The incorporation of the active phase on the walls of
64 the monolithic substrate, ideally in the form of thin layers, is the last stage in the
65 manufacture of a structured catalyst. The procedures currently used are, in many cases,

66 halfway between science and art. The most widely used is washcoating, through which
67 it is possible to deposit catalytic layers with thicknesses ranging from microns to
68 millimeters [15].

69 Electrochemical deposition has taken significant relevance in the last years as an
70 alternative technique for depositing catalytic materials, such as metals or metal oxides,
71 onto a support [16,17]. In particular, electrochemical deposition offers the possibility to
72 precisely control the thickness and morphology of the deposited catalyst layer [18]. This
73 control is crucial for optimizing catalyst performance and ensuring uniform coverage of
74 the monolith walls [19].

75 Aiming at catalytic processes where the above resulting materials could be
76 applied, dry reforming of methane (DRM) is of significant interest due to the fact it
77 simultaneously addresses two critical environmental and economic challenges, the
78 reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the production of valuable syngas, a well-
79 known precursor for various chemicals and fuels [20,21]. However, its implementation
80 has been hindered by the lack of a stable catalyst under the reaction conditions. Without
81 a catalyst, the reaction rate is limited, and the process is not economically viable. To
82 overcome this limitation, catalysts based on Pt, Rh, Pd, Ru and Ir have been explored
83 for DRM [22-24].

84 Despite the effectiveness of noble metals, their high cost and limited availability
85 have spurred research into the use of transition metals such as Co and Ni, which are
86 commonly employed in DRM due to their high catalytic activity [27]. However, these
87 transition metal-based catalysts tend to deactivate rapidly due to the deposition of coke.
88 Among these catalysts, nickel has exhibited the most remarkable performance owing to
89 its strong capacity to break C–H bonds and activate methane [26]. Regrettably, catalysts

90 based on nickel are prone to carbon deposition to a greater extent than noble metal
91 catalysts, resulting in rapid deactivation and blockage of the reactor bed [25,26].

92 In order to mitigate carbon deposition, numerous strategies have been suggested
93 to modify the chemical characteristics of nickel. These include incorporating a
94 secondary metal, particularly a noble metal, to influence the mechanism of coke
95 formation [27,28], and regulating the size of nickel particles through adjustments in the
96 preparation process [29-32], among others.

97 Enhancing the oxidation of coke is recognized as an effective approach to
98 extend the lifespan of Ni-based catalysts. Consequently, CeO₂, known for its substantial
99 oxygen storage capacity (OSC), is frequently selected as the catalyst support in dry
100 reforming reactions [33].

101 There is already a few literature devoted to dry reforming of methane using
102 cordierite monoliths as support of Ni-Ce based catalysts [34], including our own works
103 [35,36]. Nevertheless, it is surprising the lack of similar studies in which the Ni-based
104 structured catalysts were manufactured from 3D-printed supports, those available being
105 made of other materials than metals, for example Al₂O₃ [37]. Also interesting, a very
106 recent work reported on 3D-printed carbon monoliths as support of NiO-CeO₂ catalysts
107 but for a different reaction such as CO₂ methanation [38].

108 In a previous paper we published the results of preparing stainless-steel
109 honeycomb monoliths by 3D-printing and using them as a structured support of a
110 Ni/CeO₂-ZrO₂ powder deposited by washcoating for DRM reaction [9]. The resulting
111 catalyst showed competitive conversions and H₂/CO ratio, being also stable in long
112 duration tests. In this work, taking advantage of the conductivity of stainless-steel
113 metallic monoliths manufactured by 3D-printing, the electrodeposition of an active
114 phase containing Ni and Ce is reported, with the aim of optimizing the manufacture of

115 structured catalysts for CO₂ valorization processes such as dry reforming of methane.
116 The effect of the electrodeposition parameters on the coating properties and the catalytic
117 activity is studied, paying special attention to the influence of the electrodeposition
118 sequence of the different active phase components.

119

120 **2. Experimental section**

121

122 *2.1. Preparation of the metallic honeycomb monoliths*

123

124 The virtual models of the metallic honeycombs were designed using Blender 3.0
125 software (Fig. 1). The physical metallic monoliths were prepared by metal 3D-printing
126 via Laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) using an EOS M290 machine equipped with a
127 400 W Yb laser fibre and F-theta lens control. The laser beam had a diameter of
128 100 µm. To prevent oxidation of the monoliths during manufacturing, the oxygen
129 content inside the printing chamber was kept below 1% by using a variable nitrogen
130 flux.

131 The fabrication was performed using EOS Stainless Steel PH1 as raw material, a
132 pre-alloyed stainless steel in fine powder form with a maximum particle size of 63 µm
133 (Sieve analysis according to DIN ISO 4497 or ASTM B214). The chemical composition
134 of EOS Stainless Steel PH1 conforms to that of DIN 1.4540 and UNS S15500 (see
135 Table 1). This steel type offers excellent corrosion resistance and outstanding
136 mechanical properties, particularly in its precipitation-hardened state. It is commonly
137 used in various engineering applications requiring high hardness, strength, and
138 corrosion resistance.

139 The honeycomb monoliths were constructed in the vertical direction employing
140 certified parameters provided by EOS, with a layer thickness of 40 μm , using a building
141 platform pre-heated at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in nitrogen atmosphere. The stainless steel powder was
142 shaped into the solid metallic monoliths on the manufacturing platform via
143 transformation of the virtual model with the desired geometric characteristics (see Table
144 2). The metallic monoliths were detached from the building platform using a
145 semiautomatic double-column sawing machine equipped with Istech Smart 290SA
146 linear guides. To relieve the strain introduced during 3D printing, the monoliths
147 underwent further thermal treatment in nitrogen at 525 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 hours. Fig. 1 illustrates
148 examples of the 3D-printed stainless steel honeycombs (SSH) manufactured in this
149 work. The honeycomb monoliths were fabricated with four distinct cell geometries
150 (square, hexagonal, circular, and triangular), each available in two cell densities. The
151 geometric properties are detailed in Table 2. All the monoliths were 2.5 cm in length
152 with a circular cross-section of 2 cm in diameter, and their weight varied between 12
153 and 20 g depending on the cell geometry and density.

154

155 *2.2. Preparation of the catalysts*

156

157 The active phases were electrochemically deposited onto the surfaces of the
158 monoliths using a Teflon cell, different electrolytes and a two-electrode configuration.
159 The monoliths served as the working electrode, while a stainless-steel tube acted as the
160 counter electrode. The electrolytes used were prepared from 0.5 M aqueous solutions of
161 nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, 98.5%) and cerium nitrate nonahydrate
162 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99%). The monoliths were standing on a copper plate acting as contact
163 between the monoliths and the cables coming from an Autolab PGSTAT302N

164 potentiostat/galvanostat. The external lateral surface of the monoliths was masked with
165 Teflon tape. The prepared system was left for 20 min at open circuit potential for
166 stabilization. Then, the active phases were deposited on the surfaces inside the channels
167 and on the upper face applying 1 mA/cm^2 for 390 s and 780 s. Voltage responses are in
168 the range 3-5 volts. Finally, calcination at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h (heating rate of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/min}$) was
169 applied after each electrodeposition step. Fig. S1 (Supporting Information) shows an
170 image of the experimental set up. In total four different structured catalysts were
171 prepared by this procedure as a function of the active phase deposited: one containing
172 cerium alone (Ce/SSH), another with only nickel (Ni/SSH), and two of them containing
173 both elements, either introduced sequentially (Ce first) (Ni/Ce/SSH) or simultaneously
174 (Ni-Ce/SSH). Unless indicated, they were obtained using 3D-printed stainless-steel
175 honeycombs having square cells and high cells density, and after 390 s of
176 electrodeposition. Table 3 summarizes all the catalysts prepared, including the weight
177 gain related to the incorporated active phase and its adherence estimated as described
178 below. To check the validity of the electrodeposition procedure with independence of
179 the honeycomb geometry, an extra Ni/Ce/SSH catalyst was prepared using the SSH
180 support having a high cell density of circular channels.

181

182 *2.3. Catalysts characterization*

183

184 Coating adherence was estimated from the weight loss after immersion of the
185 honeycomb monoliths in petroleum ether under ultrasonication (30 min) as this method
186 is the most commonly used and most appropriate to measure the coating adherence on
187 metallic substrates [39]. The prepared catalysts were also characterized by X-ray micro-
188 fluorescence (XRF) in a Bruker S4 Pioneer spectrophotometer.

189 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images were acquired by FEGSEM in a
190 Nova NanoSEM 450 microscope operating at 30 kV. Complementary EDX
191 compositional analysis spectra were also recorded in the same instrument. Particle size
192 of Ni active phase was estimated from direct observation of SEM images, using ImageJ
193 analysis software and considering approximately 100 individual particles.

194 X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were performed at room temperature on a
195 Bruker D8 Advance A25 powder diffractometer operating with Cu K α radiation and
196 LINXEYE detector. The 2θ angle ranged from 5° to 90°, with scanning steps of 0.02°
197 and a counting time per step of 0.5 s.

198 X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) spectra were acquired using a Kratos
199 Axis Ultra DLD instrument. Metallic monoliths were sectioned and fixed on a double-
200 sided carbon tape. Given the magnetic nature of the samples, only electrostatic lenses
201 were employed for spectral acquisition. To avoid overlap between iron Auger peaks and
202 primary photoelectron signals from cerium and nickel (Ce 3d and Ni 2p),
203 monochromatic Mg K α radiation ($h\nu = 1253.6$ eV) was utilized, with the X-ray source
204 operating at 150 W. The analyzer was configured in Fixed Analyzer Transmission
205 (FAT) mode with pass energies of 40 eV and 80 eV for high-resolution and low-
206 resolution survey spectra, respectively. Data were processed with CasaXPS software
207 (version 2.3.23PR1.0, Casa Software Ltd., Devon, UK). Fitting procedures for Ce 3d
208 and Ni 2p was performed as described in [40].

209 Finally, H₂ Temperature-Programmed Reduction (H₂-TPR) analysis was
210 performed in a tubular quartz reactor coupled to a mass spectrometer (Pfeiffer model
211 QSM 200 M2), using monolith walls pieces (200 mg) and working with a 60 ml/min
212 flow of H₂(5%)/Ar and a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Before TPR, the sample was pre-

213 cleaned in O₂(5%)/He (60 ml/min) at 500 °C for 1 h, cooled down to room temperature
214 and maintained at this temperature in He for 30 min.

215

216 2.4. Catalytic tests

217

218 The catalytic performance of the different monoliths, both in their bare form and
219 after being coated by electrodeposition, was assessed in a quartz reactor operating with
220 entire monoliths at atmospheric pressure and, unless indicated, at a fixed temperature of
221 750 °C. The evaluation employed a 1:1 gas mixture of CH₄ and CO₂ as feedstock and a
222 total flow of 50 ml/min. In all cases, a pre-treatment was applied to the monoliths under
223 a 50 ml/min flow of H₂(5%)/Ar at 750 °C for 2 h. Gas analysis at the reactor's inlet and
224 outlet was performed using gas chromatography (Bruker 450-GC). Reactant (CH₄ and
225 CO₂) conversion values were determined based on the molar fractions of the individual
226 gases at the inlet and outlet, utilizing the following equations (1)–(2):

$$227 \quad \text{CH}_4 \text{ Conversion (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{[\text{CH}_4]_{\text{inlet}} - [\text{CH}_4]_{\text{outlet}}}{[\text{CH}_4]_{\text{inlet}}} \quad (1)$$

$$228 \quad \text{CO}_2 \text{ Conversion (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{[\text{CO}_2]_{\text{inlet}} - [\text{CO}_2]_{\text{outlet}}}{[\text{CO}_2]_{\text{inlet}}} \quad (2)$$

229 We corrected the molar fractions at the outlet of the reactor to account for the
230 volumetric change induced by the DRM reaction.

231 For selected samples, complementary reaction tests were performed with the
232 same conditions above with double flow (100 ml/min).

233 Finally, TPO experiments were carried out for some post-reaction samples in the
234 same equipment used for the TPR analysis and over similar sample pieces. A 60 ml/min
235 flow of O₂(5%)/He without pre-treatment was used, heating at 10 °C/min from room
236 temperature up to 900 °C and keeping this temperature for 1 h.

237

238 **3. Results and discussion**

239

240 *3.1. Selection of the optimum support for the electrodeposition*

241

242 Before running the electrodeposition, a preliminary study was conducted to
243 select the most convenient 3D-printed support among those previously obtained taking
244 into account their geometric differences (Table 2). The criterion was to test them in the
245 DRM reaction at 750 °C and choose the most active one at the same experimental
246 conditions. Our previous work had demonstrated that the bare metallic honeycombs
247 could have significant activity (values of ca. 40% and 20% for CO₂ and CH₄ conversion,
248 respectively, after 6 h of reaction at 900 °C) due to the intrinsic nickel content of the
249 stainless steel employed for their 3D-printing [9]. In this sense, we first investigated the
250 influence of geometry. Fig. 2 shows the results of this comparative study, selecting for
251 each honeycomb-type the highest cells density. All the bare monoliths were active, with
252 conversions ranging from 23 to 42 % for methane and between 24 and 53 % for CO₂,
253 both after 24 h at 750 °C. In any case, the honeycomb with square cells exhibited the
254 best overall performance. This finding agrees with previous results in the literature for
255 ceramic substrates, which concluded that, from an overall performance and
256 manufacturability point of view the square cell offers the best compromise, being
257 considered the industry standard [41]. Thus, in the second step the influence of the cells
258 density was studied for this geometry. As can also be seen in Fig. 2, the one with high
259 density (400 cpsi) behaved clearly better than that with low density (230 cpsi).
260 Therefore, the former was the monolith (SSH) selected for the remainder of the work,
261 unless indicated otherwise.

262

263 *3.2. Characterization of the 3D-printed monoliths before and after electrodeposition*

264

265 The 3D-printed bare monolith (SSH) and the subsequent Ni and Ce
266 electrodeposited catalysts (Ni/Ce/SSH and Ni-Ce/SSH samples) underwent examination
267 of their morphological structures through scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and
268 their chemical compositions were determined via EDX analysis. A representative SEM
269 image of SSH is shown in Fig. 3 and confirms the unique feature of 3D-printing
270 technology to generate samples which exhibit a rough surface. This is an additional
271 advantage with respect to metallic monoliths prepared by the most frequent design
272 which is based on rolling and piling up alternate corrugated and flat strips, submitting
273 them subsequently to high temperature calcination in order to generate a superficial
274 alumina whisker covering when a Fe-Cr-Al alloy is used as support [39]. In our case,
275 notice the presence of particles with a spherical shape on the surface which are of two
276 types. Those with less roughness are composed of a mixture of chromium and iron. By
277 contrast, the particles with higher roughness belong to an iron-rich phase, as can be seen
278 from the corresponding elemental map. Also noteworthy, the associated EDX analysis
279 is reasonably consistent with the chemical composition of the stainless steel used (Table
280 1). This scenario changed after electrodeposition for 390 s of a Ni and Ce-containing
281 phase (Figs. 4-5). As can be seen, the modified 3D-printed monoliths exhibited the
282 growth of a new phase with different texture over the support, which was confirmed by
283 EDX analysis. Both chemical maps and spectra recorded for selected area revealed the
284 presence of Ce and Ni elements although their content was higher in the catalyst
285 prepared in two steps. Also remarkable, in Ni/Ce/SSH (Fig. 4) we observed that cerium
286 consistently forms an intimate contact with chromium, creating a thin layer surrounding
287 the spherical particles. As for nickel, it appears as both small and large particles

288 deposited on top of the Ce-rich layer. In the case of Ni-Ce/SSH (Fig. 5), we observed
289 that the presence of large spherical particles, composed of a chromium-iron mixture,
290 consistently coincides with the presence of nickel and cerium. The Ni and Ce elements
291 are typically found in association with these Cr-Fe particles.

292 A complementary study by SEM-EDX of the Ce/SSH and Ni/SSH samples gave
293 results which were consistent with the above observations (see Figs. S2 and S3 in
294 Supporting Information). Also interesting, analysis of large amounts of Ni-containing
295 particles in the Ni/SSH and Ni/Ce/SSH catalysts led to histograms as those shown in
296 Fig. S4, with mean particle sizes around 200 nm.

297 Calculations based on monoliths weight gain after electrodeposition for 390 s
298 (Table 3) led to nickel loadings in good agreement with the above: 0.30% and $\leq 0.11\%$
299 for Ni/Ce/SSH and Ni-Ce/SSH, respectively. Similarly, Ni and Ce loadings estimated
300 for Ni/SSH and Ce/SSH were 0.13% and 0.96%, respectively. These results prove that
301 incorporating Ce in a first step helps increasing the amount of Ni that can be deposited.
302 Also remarkable, coating adherence values (Table 3) are in the order of those previously
303 obtained with washcoated cordierites [35,36] and are clearly higher than those reported
304 for metal honeycombs obtained through conventional corrugation procedures [42]. This
305 demonstrates again the advantage of 3D-printing in relation to the induced surface
306 roughness, which favors the anchorage of the phase to be deposited, as the SEM
307 indicated, without needing further chemical/thermal treatments [14,15,43]. Moreover,
308 the adherence values here estimated are also higher than that measured for the same 3D-
309 printed stainless steel honeycombs in a previous study where they were washcoated
310 instead of submitted to electrodeposition [9]. Also interesting, the adherence after
311 electrodeposition for 390 s was higher than that measured for the catalysts prepared by
312 electrodeposition during 780 s. For the latter, it was 71% for Ni/Ce/SSH and 74% for

313 Ni-Ce/SSH (Table 3), suggesting that a longer electrodeposition time does not
314 necessarily lead to advantaged catalysts, as we would confirm later in the catalytic tests
315 (see below).

316 Results obtained by X-ray micro-fluorescence were consistent with those found
317 by SEM-EDX. Fig. 6 collects the main data derived from XRF analysis performed in
318 multipoint mode over approx. 1.5 mm x 1.1 mm rectangle zones. Several remarks
319 should be made. First, as expected, Ce is clearly detected in Ce/SSH, while Ni present
320 in this sample, obviously at lower level, is attributable to the intrinsic content of this
321 element in the support as already commented. This also explains its detection in the
322 inner part of the monolith walls, at almost constant level (1.3-1.5 at.%) for all the
323 catalysts compared in this figure. Second, it is evident the logical increase of Ni and the
324 absence of Ce in Ni/SSH. Third, both elements are present in the external surface of the
325 monolith walls of Ni/Ce/SSH, although the atomic percentage of Ni is higher than that
326 of Ce, which also agrees with data obtained by EDX. Notice that values obtained by this
327 technique and shown in Fig. 4 were expressed as weight percentage, mass of nickel
328 being less than half of that of cerium. It should be also highlighted that both elements
329 seem to be homogeneously distributed, which suggests a good interaction between
330 them, as long as they appear with more or less similar content and ratio in all the points
331 analyzed by XRF. This situation is also consistent with the maps shown in Fig. 4.
332 Finally, similar situation is observed for Ni-Ce/SSH but notice that in this case the
333 average levels of both elements, Ni and Ce, is lower than that observed for the catalyst
334 prepared in two steps, in good agreement also with the findings from SEM-EDX and
335 weight-based calculations commented above.

336 Fig. 7 shows the XRD diagrams of all the structured catalysts prepared. The
337 diffractogram of the bare 3D-printed monolith, i.e. before electrodeposition, has also

338 been included as a reference. In general, through this technique we can only observe
339 low intense peaks which could be assigned to the stainless steel used as raw material. In
340 particular, it is possible to detect the presence of iron phases such as α (bcc,
341 ferrite/martensite) and to a lesser extent γ (fcc, austenite) [44]. The presence of other
342 steel components such as Cr, Ni or Cu cannot be discarded as they would lead to
343 reflections at very similar 2θ values. On the other hand, there is no evidence of Ni
344 and/or Ce-containing oxidized phases (such as CeO_2 or NiO). Distinguishing metallic
345 Ni is also very difficult due to the similar position of its peaks with respect to those of
346 Fe. This and the resemblance of all diffractograms with that of SSH, suggest a high
347 dispersion of the phases incorporated by electrodeposition.

348 Fig. 8 shows the main signals followed in the XPS study to investigate the
349 components of our catalysts through this technique, while Table 4 summarizes the
350 results derived from their analysis as well as the general surface composition deduced
351 from the survey spectra. Beyond detecting the expected elements present in the steel,
352 including Cr and Cu which were not considered in the mass balance for the sake of
353 simplicity, two major observations should be made. First, let us focus on the Ni/Ce
354 ratio, estimated from integrating the Ce 3d and Ni $2p_{3/2}$ signals. Employing the method
355 of Tanuma et al. [45], the Inelastic Mean Free Path (IMFP) for both signals was
356 calculated to be approximately 0.87 nm. This ensures comparable depth sensitivity for
357 both elements, which is generally considered to extend to roughly three times the IMFP.
358 Therefore, the XPS data for Ce and Ni primarily originates from the uppermost 2.6 nm
359 of the surface. If we compare the values obtained for Ni-Ce/SHH and Ni/Ce/SSH
360 catalysts, there is a clear increase for the latter (Ni/Ce grows from 1.30 to 2.24). This is
361 consistent with the higher amount of Ni observed for this sample by SEM-EDX, XRF
362 and weight-based calculations. But this is not the only change. There are also

363 differences in the redox state of nickel. In particular, notice how while almost half of the
364 metal is reduced in both the bare support and the co-electrodeposited catalyst, none of
365 Ni^0 is detected in Ni/Ce/SSH. Moreover, XPS analysis serves also to distinguish
366 between two nickel oxidized species, NiO and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$, whose relative content also
367 fluctuates from one sample to the other. Regarding the Ce 3d signal there is also some
368 difference in the oxidation state of cerium as function of the order of Ni incorporation.
369 In the catalyst prepared by sequential deposition more Ce^{4+} is observed (37% versus
370 15%).

371 Results obtained by TPR are shown in Fig. 9. Considering that, as we saw in a
372 previous study [9], reduction suffered by the stainless steel support is almost negligible
373 during these experiments, signals observed (water formed upon hydrogen consumption)
374 can be attributed to reduction of Ni^{2+} (peaks at low temperature) and ceria species
375 (small contributions at higher temperatures) [46]. Entering into details, upon cerium
376 electrodeposition (Ce/SSH sample) a poorly defined reduction event seems to occur
377 between approx. 250 °C and 500 °C. Though some contribution related to oxidized Ni
378 species from the support cannot be discarded, the position of this broad and low intense
379 peak reasonably allows assignment to reduction of very small and well-dispersed
380 crystallites of ceria [46]. This would explain the absence of ceria peaks in the
381 corresponding XRD diagram commented above.

382 After nickel electrodeposition onto this ceria-coated monolith a clear intense
383 peak of water evolution centred at 275 °C is observed, which could be thoughtfully
384 related to both NiO and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ reduction, according to XPS results. Note that this
385 peak had its maximum at much higher temperature (370 °C) for a Ni-based catalyst
386 supported onto the same 3D-printed stainless steel monoliths in a previous study [9],
387 with the difference that in that case the active phase was deposited by washcoating and

388 its support was ceria-zirconia instead of ceria. A relatively similar TPR profile was
389 found for the same catalyst but washcoated onto cordierite honeycombs [36]. In that
390 work the shift of the maxima of reduction peaks towards higher temperatures with
391 respect to the powder was attributed to some chemical interaction of nickel and the
392 mixed oxide support with the alumina employed for the washcoating. Comparison with
393 these references point to an advantage of electrodeposition versus washcoating for
394 preparing Ni-based DRM catalysts: it allows selecting lower catalyst activation
395 temperatures to guarantee that the entire nickel and most of the cerium contained in the
396 samples are in a reduced form, a well-known prerequisite to obtain better catalytic
397 performance [47,48]. In any case, we opted in this work for a reduction pre-treatment at
398 750 °C for 2 h (see experimental section) for a softer shift toward the reaction
399 conditions.

400 Regarding the catalyst prepared by Ni and Ce co-electrodeposition, the most
401 significant observation is the absence of the peak around 300 °C attributable to
402 reduction of Ni²⁺-based species. The profile, clearly shifted to higher temperature, could
403 be reasonably explained as due to reduction of a phase containing nickel and ceria in
404 strong interaction, but note the low intensity of the spread signal in any case. These
405 observations fit well with the lower content of both elements measured by SEM-EDX.
406 Let us also recall that according to XPS half of the nickel present in this sample was
407 already reduced as Ni⁰ (Table 4). This might also contribute to the flatter look of its
408 TPR curve.

409 Finally, it is evident the resemblance of the TPR profile of Ni/SSH with that of
410 Ni/Ce/SSH. Judiciously we can also interpret it as result of Ni²⁺-containing compounds
411 reduction, being the lower relative intensity of the signal a logical consequence of the

412 lower amount of Ni according to XRF compositional analysis and loading estimates
413 from weight gain after electrodeposition as commented above.

414

415 *3.3. Study of the performance in dry reforming of methane reaction*

416

417 Fig. 10 shows the evolution with reaction time of both CH₄ and CO₂ conversion
418 in the DRM process for the four catalysts prepared operating at the same experimental
419 conditions, i.e. 750 °C, equimolar reactants ratio and a flow of 50 ml/min. As a
420 reference, the result of the test with the bare monolithic support is also included.

421 Several comments should be made about the results shown in Fig. 10. First,
422 notice that in general CO₂ conversion is higher than CH₄ conversion. This is a typical
423 finding in DRM due to the occurrence in parallel of Reverse Water Gas Shift Reaction
424 (RWGS) [36]. In any case, this effect is minimal in the case of the most active catalyst,
425 Ni/Ce/SSH. Second, and more important, it is the difference observed among the
426 catalysts prepared. At this regard, notice how electrodeposition of nickel alone hardly
427 improves the performance of the bare support, only a slight increase of CH₄ conversion
428 after equivalent times of reaction is observed. This might mean that the nickel
429 incorporated (Fig. 6) covers the intrinsic active sites of the support, at least partly (Fig.
430 S3), while the new sites are similar in activity. Moreover, electrodeposition of cerium
431 alone leads to a poorer behaviour than that of the bare monolith. This suggests that the
432 electrodeposited Ce-containing phase must be less active than that containing Ni, as
433 expected, and cover active sites of the support to a large extent (Fig. S2). Particularly
434 outstanding is the performance of Ni/Ce/SSH, for which both reactant conversions
435 reach levels above 90% just after 3 h of reaction and remain stable for all the period
436 examined (up to 44 h). These results are equally remarkable when compared to those

437 obtained for Ni/CeO₂ systems in powder form. M. Yu et al. reported in a previous study
438 the catalytic behavior in dry reforming of methane of a 10%molNi/CeO₂ catalyst
439 prepared by impregnation [49]. In reaction tests carried out at 760 °C with a CH₄:CO₂
440 feed similar to that used in our case (1:1, 50mL/min), these catalysts showed initial CH₄
441 and CO₂ conversion values of 83% and 90%, respectively, which decrease to 75% and
442 85% after 44 h of reaction, and to 67% and 80% after the first 100 h. While
443 comparisons of catalytic results across different laboratories should be interpreted with
444 caution, the conversion values and reduced stability observed in these powder systems
445 contrast markedly with the excellent performance exhibited by the Ni/Ce/SSH catalyst.

446 The above means that cerium electrodeposition before that of nickel does have a
447 remarkable positive effect on the catalytic response of the latter. As we observed
448 through the catalysts characterization discussed in the previous section, more nickel
449 seems to enter over the monolith in this case, which might be a reasonable explanation
450 for this improvement, although the additional positive influence of a Ni-Ce interaction
451 cannot be discarded according to XRF results. Also remarkable, increasing the time of
452 electrodeposition does not enhance the activity of this sample. See Table 5 in which the
453 main results obtained in the whole catalytic study, including the effect of
454 electrodeposition time, has been summarized. In other words, short time (390 s) is
455 enough to obtain an outstanding performance. Finally, co-electrodeposition leads to the
456 worst catalyst as almost no activity (conversions lower than 15%) was observed for Ni-
457 Ce/SSH sample, even after 44 h of reaction, while doubling the electrodeposition time
458 just served to reach similar conversions to those of Ni/SSH (Table 5).

459 As we can see in Table 5, we also tested a sample prepared by sequential Ni and
460 Ce electrodeposition over a 3D-printed metal honeycomb having high density of
461 circular channels, the worst geometry according to the preliminary tests shown in Fig. 2.

462 Noticeable, we found a similar performance to that observed for the structured catalyst
463 with square channels just discussed. This demonstrates the strength of the
464 electrodeposition procedure proposed in this work.

465 Also remarkable, no CO₂ evolution was detected during TPO experiments over
466 Ni/Ce/SSH and Ni-Ce/SSH after reaction (Fig. S5), which denotes that carbon deposits,
467 if formed, must be negligible.

468 The most active catalyst, Ni/Ce/SSH, was also tested under more severe reaction
469 conditions as shown in Fig. S6. We checked the effect of doubling the reactants flow in
470 the middle of the process, finding how after an initial slight decrease of CH₄ and CO₂
471 conversions they both recover their previous trend reaching finally the levels they had
472 attained without this alteration. It should be highlighted that this additional test was
473 consecutively carried out with the same piece of Ni/Ce/SSH, i.e. after experiments
474 shown in Fig. 10. This proves its extremely high stability in the DRM process.

475

476 *3.4. On the influence of the electrodeposition sequence*

477

478 The mechanism of the electrodeposition process is described on the basis of
479 equations (3) and (4) [50,51]. The reduction of nitrate ions, equation (3), proceeds on
480 the surface of the electrode acting as a cathode, and produces hydroxide ions at the
481 electrode/solution interface, locally increasing the pH within the so-called Nernst
482 diffusion layer. Thus, the OH⁻ concentration reaches its maximum very close to the
483 electrode surface and decreases down to negligible values at a certain distance from the
484 electrode surface due to the precipitation of metal hydroxides, equation (4).

487 In the case of the electrolytes employed here, the cations involved are Ni²⁺ and
488 Ce³⁺, and the stoichiometry of the products is shown in equations (5) and (6). As can be
489 inferred, the amount of OH⁻ ions required to obtain a mol of metal precipitated from the
490 precursor solution depends on the stoichiometry of the hydroxide.

493 Notwithstanding, it is found in the literature that the actual deposits are complex
494 oxyhydroxides, comprising both oxides and hydroxides [52,53]. On the other hand,
495 direct reduction of Ni²⁺ to Ni⁰ cannot be completely discarded. In fact, let us recall XPS
496 results (Table 4), which indicated a significant presence of Ni⁰ in the Ni-Ce/SSH
497 catalyst. However, such content was very similar to that of the SSH sample which
498 means it could be mainly related to the intrinsic nickel of the honeycomb support. In
499 this sense, the no detection of Ni⁰ in Ni/Ce/SSH might be another proof of the higher
500 incorporation of nickel in this sample, so covering the substrate. Moreover, the literature
501 reports that the reduction of Ni²⁺ to Ni⁰ (metallic nickel electrodeposition) is achieved
502 using electrolytes such as sulfate, acetate, sulfamate, ammonium sulfite, ammonium
503 tartrate, and the commercial Watt bath [54-56], which is not our case. Therefore, we
504 believe that the extent of nitrate reduction is significantly more prominent in our system
505 compared to the potential direct reduction of Ni²⁺.

506 The rate of OH⁻ production, i.e. pH increase within the diffusion layer, depends
507 on the applied current, I, and, therefore, also on the deposition voltage, V, by the Butler-
508 Volmer equation. The electro-generation of hydroxides is assumed to be fast enough to
509 form the oxyhydroxides almost instantaneously [50].

510 When two different metallic cations are present, there is competition for the
511 available OH⁻ ions and the thermodynamic difference between the two metal hydroxide

512 precipitation reactions is the key factor governing the composition of the
513 electrodeposited product [51,57]. The thermodynamic aspects of the precipitation
514 reactions can be analyzed employing the stability constant of the products, as reported
515 by J. Yang et al. [57]. Thus, the molar ratios of Ce/Ni depend on the applied current,
516 which determines the pH in the diffusion layer, but also on the temperature and the pH
517 of the bulk electrolyte. Therefore, the compositions of the yielded solid mixed-metal
518 oxyhydroxides are different from the metal concentration in the precursor electrolyte.

519 Other authors have also reported similar conclusions when working with Ce/Pd
520 and Ce/Pt. Ho et al. [58] performed co-electrodeposition of Pd-CeO₂ on high pore
521 density foams of FeCrAlloy but required a strict control of the deposition to avoid
522 uncontrolled formation of large Pt particles and thin CeO₂ coatings. Verlato et al. [59]
523 studied the synthesis of Pt-CeO₂ catalysts on FeCrAlloy employing three strategies: i)
524 co-electrodeposition, ii) electrodeposition of CeO₂ + electrodeposition of Pt, and iii)
525 electrodeposition of Pt + electrodeposition of CeO₂. They found that the
526 electrodeposition of Pt in the first step and CeO₂ in the second step is the best method to
527 control the size and surface distribution of Pt-particles, and CeO₂-layer thickness and
528 porosity.

529 The study of the relationship between electrodeposition variables and the
530 composition/amount of the catalyst deposited on the monoliths deserves a separate work
531 and is out of the scope of this manuscript. In any case, the need for strict control of the
532 experimental electrodeposition variables when co-depositing Ce and Ni, in order to
533 obtain adequate catalyst chemical compositions, is an argument against this approach.
534 In contrast, the sequential method, depositing Ce first and Ni later, allows the
535 preparation of catalysts that have shown very good results without the need for
536 optimization studies of their experimental parameters.

537

538 **4. Conclusions**

539

540 Through the 3D-printing technique, we were able to prepare metallic monoliths
541 of honeycomb type, which are not only supports of the active phases for DRM, but also
542 provide an activity, thanks to the intrinsic Ni content. This opens opportunities for
543 future improvements, such as modifying the composition of the steel powder.

544 Honeycombs with up to four different cells geometry (circular, triangular,
545 hexagonal and square) and two cell densities for each cell shape (ranging from 213 to
546 632 cpsi) could be prepared.

547 The deposition of the active phase (containing Ni and/or Ce) on the 3D-printed
548 honeycomb supports was found to be facile and fast (390 s) via electrodeposition
549 method. To our knowledge the combination of 3D-printing and electrodeposition for
550 catalytic purposes was a novel contribution of this work, especially for the design of
551 Dry Reforming of Methane (DRM) catalysts.

552 The use of electrochemical deposition under proper conditions, in particular
553 using a two-steps procedure (Ce first and Ni second) instead of co-electrodeposition, led
554 to a catalyst with an outstanding performance, operating with a 1:1 CH₄/CO₂ mixture at
555 750 °C and atmospheric pressure, in terms of conversion (>90%), selectivity
556 (H₂/CO=0.8) and stability over time (>44 h without deactivation). Moreover, similar
557 behavior was observed after electrodeposition over honeycombs with different cells
558 geometry proving the robustness of the preparation procedure. For example, selection as
559 substrate of honeycombs with circular channels, in principle less favorable than square
560 ones according to preliminary tests, did not penalize the performance of the catalyst
561 further electrodeposited.

562 Regarding the influence of the order of Ni incorporation with respect to Ce, most
563 characterization techniques (SEM-EDX, weight gain-based calculations, XRF, XPS and
564 TPR) pointed to a higher amount of Ni reached after sequential deposition. This alerts
565 that, although co-electrodeposition may appear at the beginning as a simpler one-stage
566 route, it is finally not convenient to reach a good DRM catalyst.

567 The results obtained suggest that the approach proposed here might have great
568 potential not only in the DRM but also in other catalytic processes by exploiting the
569 flexibility and optimizing variables of both the 3D-printing methodology (such as raw
570 material and designed geometry) and the electrodeposition technique (for example,
571 time, current density or electrolyte concentration and nature, among others).

572

573 **Credit authorship contribution statement**

574

575 **Otman Bazta:** Investigation. **María del Pilar Yeste:** Investigation. **Hilario**
576 **Vidal:** Writing – original draft. **José Manuel Gatica:** Data curation, Writing – review
577 & editing. **José Juan Calvino:** Funding acquisition, Visualization. **Juan de Dios**
578 **López-Castro:** Software. **Leandro González-Rovira:** Methodology. **Francisco Javier**
579 **Botana:** Resources. **Miguel Angel Cauqui:** Formal analysis, Supervision. **Ginesa**
580 **Blanco:** Investigation. **Juan Carlos Hernández-Garrido:** Conceptualization, Funding
581 acquisition, Project administration.

582

583 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

584

585 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
586 personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this
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588

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590

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597

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822 **Table 1**

823 Chemical composition of the EOS Stainless Steel PH1 used in this work as raw material

824 to manufacture the 3D-printed metallic honeycomb monoliths (Fe (balance)).

Element	Cr	Ni	Cu	Mn	Si	C	Mo	Nb
Min [wt.-%]	14.0	3.5	2.5	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.15
Max [wt.-%]	15.5	5.5	4.5	1.00	1.00	0.07	0.5	0.45

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826 **Table 2**

827 Geometric characteristics of the 3D-printed metallic honeycomb monoliths.

Cell geometry	Cell density			Cell spacing (mm) ^b	Wall thickness (mm) ^b	Dh (mm) ^c	GSA (cm ² /cm ³) ^c	OFA (%) ^c	Weight (g)
	cpsi ^a	Cells/cm ² ^a	Cells/cm ² ^b						
Square	230	35.7	34.4	1.65	0.36	1.3	18.9	61	12.04
Square	400	62.0	59.8	1.26	0.28	1.1	24.8	61	14.18
Hexagonal	271	42.0	38.2	1.68	0.30	1.4	19.3	68	11.85
Hexagonal	465	72.1	70.0	1.27	0.22	1.1	25.9	68	13.43
Circle	213	33.0	37.6	1.67	0.35	1.3	19.0	56	16.23
Circle	465	72.1	66.2	1.23	0.28	1.1	25.0	58	18.26
Triangle	419	64.9	61.1	1.90	0.30	0.8	26.5	53	16.62
Triangle	632	98.0	99.3	1.48	0.23	0.6	34.4	54	20.26

828 Nominal data according to the geometric model^a and experimental data^b

829 Data obtained from equations in [38]^c

830 **Table 3**

831 Time of electrodeposition, weight gain and adherence related to the active phases of the
832 prepared catalysts.

Sample	Electrodeposition time (s)	Weight gain (mg)	Adherence (%)
Ce/SSH	390	26.0	93
Ni/SSH	390	39.9	81
Ni/Ce/SSH	390	33.3 24.57 of Ce 8.73 of Ni	89
Ni/Ce/SSH	780	99.3 57.1 of Ce 42.2 of Ni	71
Ni-Ce/SSH	390	15.7	95
Ni-Ce/SSH	780	21.0	74

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834 **Table 4**

835 Main data derived from XPS analysis (atomic percentages from high resolution survey spectra excluding Cu and Cr, and atomic ratios and
836 percentage of nickel and cerium species estimated from analysis of Ni 2p_{3/2} and Ce 3d signals).

Sample	Fe 2p	C 1s	O 1s	Ni 2p _{3/2}	Ce 3d	Ni/Ce	Fe/Ni	Fe/Ce	Ni ⁰	NiO	Ni(OH) ₂	Ce ⁴⁺
SSH	2.85	69	27.7	0.45	0.00	-	6.33	-	45.4	32.4	22.2	-
Ni-Ce/SSH	3.66	65.14	30.21	0.56	0.43	1.30	6.54	8.51	49.8	15.5	34.7	15
Ni/Ce/SSH	20.05*	31.4	45.99	1.77	0.79	2.24	11.33*	25.38*	0	59.3	40.7	37

837 * The higher iron content was related to a rougher surface induced by the cut in this sample, which favored higher contribution of steel matrix.

838 **Table 5**

839 Catalytic activity results of the prepared catalysts in the DRM reaction at 750 °C with
840 CH₄/CO₂ = 1:1 and a total flow of 50 ml/min. Data for the bare support are also
841 included as a reference.

Sample	CH₄ Conversion (%)	CO₂ Conversion (%)	H₂/CO Ratio
SSH ¹	33	42	0.41
Ce/SSH ^{a,1}	4	8	0.31
Ni/SSH ^{a,1}	41	44	0.30
Ni-Ce/SSH ^{a,2}	15	15	0.37
Ni-Ce/SSH ^{b,2}	34	43	0.42
Ni/Ce/SSH ^{a,2}	95	97	0.76
Ni/Ce/SSH ^{b,2}	94	96	0.79
Ni/Ce/SSH ^{a,2,*}	97	98	0.71

842 Electrodeposition time = 390 s^a or 780 s^b

843 Data at 12¹ or 44² hours TOS

844 * SSH with high density of circular (instead of square) channels

Figure Captions

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847 **Fig. 1.** An illustrative virtual model for the creation of one of the types of honeycomb
848 monoliths (a) and images of some of the metallic honeycomb monoliths obtained by
849 3D-printing with different cell density (b,c) and geometry (d-g).

850 **Fig. 2.** Reactants conversion and H₂/CO ratio in the DRM reaction for the bare 3D-
851 printed metallic honeycombs with high cells density and the indicated geometries after
852 24 h at 750 °C under CH₄/CO₂ = 1:1 and a total flow of 50 ml/min. For the monoliths
853 with square cells results for the honeycomb with low cells density are also included.

854 **Fig. 3.** SEM image and EDX analysis, including elemental maps, corresponding to a
855 piece of the bare 3D-printed metallic honeycomb monolith (SSH) used as catalytic
856 support.

857 **Fig. 4.** SEM image and EDX analysis, including elemental maps, corresponding to a
858 piece of the Ni/Ce/SSH structured catalyst prepared by electrodeposition for 390 s.

859 **Fig. 5.** SEM image and EDX analysis, including elemental maps, corresponding to a
860 piece of the Ni-Ce/SSH structured catalyst prepared by electrodeposition for 390 s.

861 **Fig. 6.** Compositional analysis by X-ray micro-fluorescence of Ce/SSH, Ni/SSH, Ni-
862 Ce/SSH and Ni/Ce/SSH (catalysts prepared by electrodeposition for 390 s). For each
863 sample the graph at the left corresponds to an inner part of a monolith wall while that at
864 the right comes from the external surface of a monolith wall, as illustrated by the image
865 at the top. Blue and red dots correspond to Ni and Ce, respectively.

866 **Fig. 7.** X-ray diffraction diagrams obtained for all the catalysts prepared by
867 electrodeposition (390 s) as well as that of the bare monolithic support for comparison.

868 **Fig. 8.** Ni 2p_{3/2} (left) and Ce 3d (right) XPS signals. In the former, purple, red and green
869 deconvoluted peaks correspond to Ni⁰, NiO and Ni(OH)₂, respectively, while green
870 deconvoluted peaks in the latter relate to Ce⁴⁺.

871 **Fig. 9.** TPR profiles (m/z 18 signal) of the catalysts prepared by electrodeposition (390
872 s), obtained under H₂(5%)/Ar gas mixture and a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

873 **Fig. 10.** Evolution with reaction time of the reactants conversion in the DRM reaction
874 for the catalysts prepared by electrodeposition during 390 s working at 750 °C with
875 CH₄/CO₂ = 1:1 and a total flow of 50 ml/min. The profiles for the bare support are also
876 included as a reference.

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 10

Supporting Information

Novel combination of 3D-printing and electrochemical deposition to design and prepare metallic honeycomb supported catalysts for dry reforming of methane

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Fig. S1. Images of the experimental setup for the electrodeposition process.

Fig. S2. SEM image and EDX elemental maps corresponding to a piece of the Ce/SSH structured catalyst prepared by electrodeposition for 390 s.

Fig. S3. SEM image and EDX elemental maps corresponding to a piece of the Ni/SSH structured catalyst prepared by electrodeposition for 390 s.

Fig. S4. Particles size distribution obtained by direct analysis of Ni-containing particles in the SEM images of Ni/SSH and Ni/Ce/SSH catalysts, and example of image used to generate the histograms.

Fig. S5. TPO profiles (m/z 44 signal) after reaction of the Ni/Ce/SSH and Ni-Ce/SSH catalysts prepared by electrodeposition for 390 s.

Fig. S6. Consecutive response in the DRM reaction ($\text{CH}_4/\text{CO}_2=1$) of the Ni/Ce/SSH catalyst (prepared by electrodeposition during 390 s) to a change in the flow at 750 °C.

Fig. S1.

Fig. S2.

Fig. S3.

Fig. S4

Fig.S5

Fig. S6